

LOVE model-based assessment of teaching practices within industrial engineering master programs in Poland and Thailand

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Abstract

The objective of the paper is to compare teaching approaches and practices that are used on master programs within industrial engineering and related fields. The comparison is made on selected Polish and Thai universities that provided students and graduates for the research survey. Students and graduates from four Polish and six Thai universities have participated in the survey in academic year of 2018/2019. The programs of their studies were master level programs with direct relation to industrial engineering. The teaching methods within the study are structured and classified within the framework of the LOVE model – a learning experience-based model that serves for the assessment and classification of teaching methods. The comparison is based on the students' assessment of their experiences related to the specific teaching methods used within the course of their studies. The comparative analysis criteria come from the classification of teaching methods to one of the following experience-oriented categories: L – learning, O – observing, V – visiting and E – experimenting. The results are interpreted regarding the coverage of specific experience categories within the studying program, relation between the presence and assessment score of specific methods and categories and cross-country analysis of the results. The preliminary results of the study show that there is a significant difference between the viewpoints and perceptions of the students from two compared countries on the teaching methods. Polish students expressed that the top three most efficient methods are guided practical exercises, laboratory classes and discussion. For Thai students, lectures, case studies and discussion were rated as the top three most efficient methods. With the LOVE model classification, it seems that Polish students appreciate learning and experimenting, while for Thai students it's a mixture of observing and learning experiences.

Keywords: active learning, industrial engineering, teaching and learning methods, quality in higher education, LOVE model.

1 Introduction

The concept of the paper is based on two key features: 1) experience-based approach to the assessment of teaching and learning methods (TLMs) and 2) comparison of Polish and Thailand students with respect their preferences on TLMs. The first feature is applied through LOVE model. It is a learning experience-based model that serves for the assessment and classification of teaching methods applied in engineering-oriented education. LOVE model is originally presented by its authors (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap 2017a), but it is important to present its background and underpinned concepts and its building blocks. First of all, model is oriented on students experience and in that sense it follows the principles of experience economy 4E model as developed by Pine and Gilmour (1998) and transfers them to the field of engineering education. Secondly, vast catalogue of TLMs classified within four categories of LOVE model make it more a tool for assessment of whole curricula and programs than of single courses. Bearing that in mind, LOVE model should be referred to active learning strategies (Freeman et al. 2014; Christie and Graaff 2017; Lima et al. 2017a), curriculum development pathways (Hodge et al. 2008; Healey and Jenkins 2009; McTighe and Wiggins 2012) or designing teaching and learning approach methodologies (Dunlosky et al. 2013; Mesquita et al. 2015; Lima et al. 2017b) that aim at grabbing whole studying programs and design its learning outcomes. Thirdly, the idea behind LOVE model is to provide guidance for curriculum designers on how to deliver diversified and meaningful experience for students in order to make them not only valuable graduates, but also good

researchers (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap 2018). Such an approach has a very long history and is commonly recognized in literature (Hodge et al. 2008; Healey and Jenkins 2009; Wallin et al. 2017) and in practice, especially in engineering education, and has many different variants or implementation strategies. Finally, LOVE model contributes to the vast and diversified field of engineering education assessment and classification, with a specific focus on teaching and learning methods. Perhaps, the scope of classification and assessment is quite original, since it is the experience of students in relation to the TLMs applied, but it could be easily adopted to serve for mainstream assessment and classification toolbox. Example of classification criteria to be applied in engineering education are numerous, but just to give an example we could refer to Bloom’s revised taxonomy (Krathwohl 2002) that provides framework for classification of program learning outcomes and for designing the development strategy of a curriculum. Both, LOVE model and Bloom’s taxonomy are capable of providing specific guidelines for designing the curriculum, but each one of them is focused on its different elements or aspects. The assessment and evaluation of studying programs is even more complex issue with a huge reporting on its application. Obviously, LOVE model based assessment is not available yet. The scope of our paper, if considered from more general perspective, could be faced towards educational approach or TLM assessment. In the literature, there are many results of researches and assessment presented, focusing for example on active or research approach (Freeman et al. 2014; Wallin et al. 2017) or meta-analysis of assessments (Wieman 2014).

The model applies the following experience-oriented categories: L – learning, O – observing, V – visiting and E – experimenting. Detailed classification of teaching and learning methods according to LOVE model is presented in Figure . The model has been developed quite recently (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap 2017a) but has been already widely discussed in the literature and applied for assessment and development of studying programs (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap 2017b, a, 2018; Koomsap et al. 2019).

The key recommendation from the creators of the LOVE model is to provide diversified learning experiences throughout studying period in order to achieve complex attitude towards gaining new knowledge and competences. In other words, each one of the experience categories should be significantly represented in educational program as a whole, and in each one of its components. On the other hand, none of the experience types is strong enough to provide complex and meaningful transfer of knowledge and competences. Finally, the assumption of LOVE model is to give more attention to immersive and active types of learning experiences in order to make them more efficient while studying outcomes, namely competences and knowledge are concerned.

 E-Experimenting (active immersion)	
1. Field classes, trips and excursions 2. Conference 3. Virtual reality	1. Project-based learning (PjBL) 2. Laboratory classes 3. Virtual laboratory
 L-Learning (active absorption)	
1. Lecture 2. Guided conversation 3. Integrated or interdisciplinary teaching 4. Showing video material 5. Seminars conducted in classes 6. Live lecture from a remote place	1. Discussion 2. Demonstration with exercising 3. Class debate 4. Small groups debate 5. Simulation 6. Problem-based learning (PrBL) 7. Programmed teaching 8. Workshop 9. Brainstorming 10. Case study 11. Online interactive learning 12. Game-based learning 13. Guided practical exercises 13. Role play 14. Assignments 15. Individual presentation

Figure 1. Classification of teaching and learning methods in LOVE model (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya et al. 2019)

The scope of the paper is limited to the comparison of Polish and Thai master students and graduates of industrial engineering related programs. The comparison is focused on student's assessment of teaching and learning methods used during their education process. The comparison is based on students and graduates responses and is focused on comparing the coverage for specific TLMs with its assessment with respect to make students learning experience more efficient and meaningful. In order to standardize the types of experiences while studying LOVE model is used. The selection of the two countries for performing comparative studies is made on the practical possibilities of accessing the students and graduates to complete survey. It is also connected to the assumption that these two countries could significantly differ with regard to the student's approach of TLMs. The additional objective of the paper is to verify the usefulness of LOVE model and the results of its application for such a comparative study with students responds as a major data source.

2 Research methodology

The survey was conducted in the form of computer assisted web interview (CAWI) in the period of October – December 2018. The comparative sample consisted of 100 Thai and 89 Polish respondents. Table 1 presents basic characteristics of the surveyed sample of students. Basic differences between Polish and Thai students samples are related to its age structure (more diversified in Thailand while in Poland most of the students are entering university right after their secondary education) and related to it academic status (in Thailand only half of the students were enrolled during the survey, while in Poland it is over 80%), and significantly bigger share of female students in Poland.

Table 1. Basic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics of respondents	PL	THA	Total
<i>Age</i>			
20 - 25	73	25	98
26 - 30	7	37	44
31 - 35	4	20	24
36 - 40	4	10	14
41 - 45	1	5	6
46 and more	0	3	3
<i>Gender</i>			
Female	60	44	104
Male	29	56	85
<i>Academic status</i>			
A Master's student on the 1st year	20	15	35
A Master's student on the 2nd year and more	43	34	77
A graduate with the Master's degree during the past 2 years	12	30	42
A graduate with the Master's degree during the past 5 years	3	16	19
A graduate with the Master's degree during the past 10 years	5	3	8
Other	6	2	8

The students of ten different universities have participated in the survey. The list of universities is presented in Table 2. The leading criterion for selection of students was their enrolment into master program of industrial engineering or related.

Table 2. List of Universities participating in surveying students

Name of the University	Country and city	Number of respondents
Asian Institute of Technology	Thailand, Bangkok	30
Lodz University of Technology	Poland, Lodz	25
Thammasat University	Thailand, Thammasat	24
Częstochowa University of Technology	Poland, Czestochowa	23
King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang	Thailand, Ladkrabang	22
Cracow University of Economics	Poland, Cracow	20
Poznan University of Economics	Poland, Poznan	19
Chiang Mai University	Thailand, Chiang Mai	16
Khon Kaen University	Thailand, Khon Kaen	4
King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok	Thailand, Bangkok	4
	Total	189

The selection of programs was based on its reference industrial engineering body of knowledge. "Industrial engineering" itself it is not so common program of studies in Poland, since it is actually offered in one university only (Otoutczelnie.pl 2020). Among similar studying programs, management and production engineering is the most popular one, having more than 10000 candidates in the past 2 academic years (MNiSW 2017, 2018). Therefore, the selection of programs for comparative analysis was widened to include the following leading topics: industrial engineering and development, industrial engineering and management, workplace safety engineering, logistics and supply chain engineering and commodity science and material engineering. According to Lima et al. (2012) all the programs included refers directly to industrial engineering and management areas of knowledge. The number of respondents with regard to studying programs is presented in Table 3. The differentiation between the programs held in Thailand and in Poland is reflected in studying period (2 years in Thailand and 1,5 year in Poland), programs structure (1 or 2 semesters dedicated to master thesis only in Thailand, while joined studying and thesis work in Poland), or number of courses and credits, but since the teaching and learning methods are the point of interest for this research, these differences are not discussed here.

Table 3. Sample structure with regard to studying program and country

Leading topics of studies	PL	THA	Total
Industrial / production engineering and management	58	37	95
Industrial engineering / development	3	57	60
Workplace safety engineering	18	0	18
Logistics and supply chain engineering	9	3	12
Other	1	3	4
Total	89	100	189

The questionnaire was designed to cover two major issues: the coverage of different teaching and learning methods in studying programs and the assessment of its effectiveness from the perspective of students. Altogether, questionnaire consisted of 6 identifying questions, 3 questions on courses and TLM applied and 1

question for open remarks. It is important to mention that the list of possible answers for question on coverage of different TLMs included all the methods from LOVE model.

3 Results of student assessment of teaching practices

As for the most applied TLMs, the lectures and guided practical exercises hold the 1st and 2nd spot both in Poland and Thailand. For Polish students, the TLMs that follows comes from learning and experimenting groups, while for Thai students, the group of learning methods together with some of the observing type of methods. The application of TLMs for Thai students seem to be more balanced while for Polish students we could observe some more significant diversity.

The results of the survey are to be interpreted for the comparing purposes between Polish and Thai students. Just to save space and keep the paper brief, the results are presented in form of combined graphs (Figure 2 and Figure 3), while the tables with results are annexed to the paper. The first look, at the results of the survey, gives the impression that there is a significant difference between the viewpoints and perceptions of the students from two compared countries on the TLMs. Figure 2 and Figure 3 compare the results of the most applied and considered to be the most efficient TLMs for Polish and Thai students respectively.

Polish students expressed that the top three most efficient methods are guided practical exercises, laboratory classes and discussion. We could observe that the efficiency assessment does not follow the intensity of TLMs applications throughout the course of the studies. For Thai students, lectures, case studies and discussion were rated as the top three most efficient methods. Here, we could observe that the efficiency assessment follows the intensity the methods are used. Despite direct relation to the preferences of students, it could be interpreted as some type of trust in teacher's selection of TLMs and perhaps more master – student relationship.

With the LOVE model classification, it seems that Polish students appreciate learning and experimenting, while for Thai students it's a mixture of observing and learning experiences.

Figure 2. Comparison between the most applied and the most efficient TLMs in engineering education from Polish students' viewpoint [n=89]

Figure 3. Comparison between the most applied and the most efficient TLMs in engineering education from Thai students' viewpoint [n=100]

For Polish students, 6 out of 10 the most efficient TLMs belong to learning experience category. For Thai students it is even more dominating with 8 out of 10 the most efficient methods belonging to learning experience category. The most significant difference comes with investigating the remaining courses in the most efficient 10. For Polish students the laboratory class is assessed as the 2nd most efficient while for Thai the lectures are assessed as the 1st most efficient ones. The remaining courses in the top 10 for Thai students belong to the observing type of activities while for Polish students it is split between observing and experimenting type of activities.

4 Discussion and conclusions

The distance between the degree of the application and the efficiency evaluation could be also interpreted as a need to increase or decrease the intensity of use of specific TLMs. The need to increase the intensity could be observed for case studies, discussion, guided practical exercises and group debate for Thai students. For Polish students its more often the case, and such a need could be observed for discussion, workshop, problem-based learning, field classes, laboratory classes, project-based learning, guided practical exercises, demonstration and exercises, case studies and some other minor cases. In general, for Polish students the differences between the application and assessment occur quite often and many cases with the possible need to decrease the intensity of specific TLMs could be also observed. It is the case for programmed teaching, brainstorming, individual presentation, assignments, online interactive learning and to some extent lectures. For Thai students the need to decrease the intensity of specific is highly visible as well. It concerns, among others, guided conversations, programmed teaching, role play, remote lectures, conferences, game-based learning and to some extent all the experimenting type of TLMs. Possibly, these type of learning experiences are not highly valued by students. The overall assessment of lectures is quite similar to the findings of Wieman (Wieman 2014) that showed significant lack of efficiency for passive learning approaches in comparison to active ones. Surprisingly, it is evidently confirmed for Polish students while not so clearly for Thai students.

The results for Thai students, concerning the application level of TLMs and to same point its assessment is similar to what have been presented from the point of view of the teachers (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya et al. 2019). As for Polish students it has never been investigated so far and the results should lie a new background for engineering educations research, as well as, LOVE model application for its assessment. The comparative analysis showed that the two samples of industrial engineering education is perceived differently by Thai and Polish students. The different content concerning TLMs leads to quite different assessment of the efficiency of specific TLMs. To get the overview of the study we could say that the studying culture could have impacted

the results by the aligning students' assessment with TLMs applications in Thailand while making it more contesting for Polish students. It seems that LOVE model is appropriate tool for that type of comparison because of its wide coverage for engineering TLMs and clear classification of the experiences gained throughout the educational process.

Since it is the curricula that are investigated the conclusions should refer to its approach while TLMs are concerned. The recommendations that comes from the study could be classified into two different groups: redefining potential and growing potential methods. First group of recommendations are the methods that need redefining its potential. These are the methods with relatively high application level with significantly lower efficiency assessment. This could be the case for learning type experience connected to such a method as assignments, individual presentations or brainstorming for Polish students, and also individual presentation, class debate or role play and game-based learning for Thai students. It seems that these types of experiences have quite a significant role to play in educational process but need to be adjusted to student's capacity and modernized through changes of approach and techniques. For Thai students it is surprising that visiting and experimenting types of TLMs could also fit to that category and should be revised in a sense of its contribution to student's competence building experiences. The category of methods that need redefining would certainly account for remote teaching methods, such as remote lectures, online interactive learning or virtual reality classes, which are not close to meet its own potential at the moment. This the case for both Thai and Polish students and should be carefully considered by curriculum developing universities, especially, in the context of epidemical threat and limitations to the direct contact classes. Again, it is difficult to find direct and clear connection to the results of other studies due to LOVE model configuration. Our results, and to some extend the LOVE model design, confirms the findings of the studies that indicate the importance of research tasks throughout the education process (Hodge et al. 2008; Wallin et al. 2017). Somehow, the results are indicating that there is no easy implementation of active learning methods and its implementation is not guaranteeing the success. As Hora (Hora 2014) claims, even passive TLMs could play its role efficient enough if well use in educational process. On the other hand, the use of active and attractive methods is not always appreciated and well perceived by students, as could be observed in some case in our research.

Second group of recommendations are the methods that should participate more in educational process due to its high significance to industrial engineering field of knowledge as well as its experience building capacity. For sure, for Polish experimenting type of experience is the most need for industrial engineering graduate and should be provided in good quality and to a proper extent. For Thai students it is more difficult to indicate the specific group of experiences that should be intensified throughout the educational process. Certainly, it is the case for some learning methods, like case studies, discussion and to some extent workshops. We could not observe such a need with reference to visiting or experimenting type of experiences.

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Table 4. Survey results for Polish students [n=89]

L/O/V/E	Teaching and Learning Method	Most Applied Teaching and Learning Method							Efficient Teaching and Learning Method							Rank		
		0	1	2	3	4	5	Sum	Mean	SD	5	4	3	2	1		Sum	Sum product
L	Discussion	12	18	31	13	11	4	89	2,06	1,34	5	12	5	3	3	28	97,00	3
	Demonstration with exercising	5	17	28	21	13	5	89	2,39	1,26	6	0	11	5	2	24	75,00	5
	Class debate	17	24	25	14	6	3	89	1,74	1,30	3	3	3	2	2	13	42,00	13
	Small group debate	6	22	22	20	14	5	89	2,33	1,33	2	3	0	6	1	12	35,00	15
	Simulation	28	26	22	11	1	1	89	1,26	1,13	1	2	6	1	2	12	35,00	16
	Problem-based learning	9	28	34	13	4	1	89	1,75	1,04	6	3	3	0	3	15	54,00	9
	Programmed teaching	24	25	24	7	7	2	89	1,48	1,30	1	0	0	1	1	3	8,00	26
	Workshop	14	18	26	21	8	2	89	1,97	1,28	2	9	8	0	9	28	79,00	4
	Brainstorming	4	13	32	24	10	6	89	2,46	1,20	2	1	1	7	1	12	32,00	19
	Case study	3	21	25	23	16	1	89	2,35	1,15	3	6	5	8	4	26	74,00	6
	Online interactive learning	19	25	24	15	6	0	89	1,60	1,19	2	0	0	4	2	8	20,00	23
	Game-based learning	34	28	18	5	3	1	89	1,08	1,13	2	1	2	2	3	10	27,00	21
	Role play	31	31	19	4	3	1	89	1,10	1,10	1	0	1	1	1	4	11,00	25
	Guided practical exercises	3	6	17	25	31	7	89	3,08	1,19	12	10	7	7	5	41	140,00	1
	Assignments	4	7	25	20	24	9	89	2,90	1,29	2	2	1	5	6	16	37,00	14
Individual presentation	5	8	27	23	22	4	89	2,69	1,22	2	1	3	4	4	14	35,00	16	
O	Lecture	5	5	8	6	40	25	89	3,64	1,41	5	0	7	2	9	23	59,00	7
	Guided conversation	7	26	19	24	12	1	89	2,12	1,23	1	8	2	4	1	16	52,00	10

	Integrated or interdisciplinary teaching	7	30	27	16	7	2	89	1,91	1,16	1	1	5	1	6	14	32,00	19
	Showing video material	8	16	21	22	19	3	89	2,42	1,33	3	3	3	4	6	19	50,00	12
	Seminars conducted in class	6	20	28	15	15	5	89	2,31	1,32	0	4	3	3	4	14	35,00	16
	Live lecture from a remote place	40	25	14	5	4	1	89	1,00	1,19	0	0	2	0	2	4	8,00	26
	Field classes, trips and excursions	32	32	10	9	5	1	89	1,17	1,24	7	1	0	5	2	15	51,00	11
V	Conference	23	29	23	8	4	2	89	1,40	1,22	3	0	1	3	1	8	25,00	22
	Virtual reality	46	21	10	8	3	1	89	0,92	1,21	0	0	1	1	2	4	7,00	28
	Project-based learning	10	12	26	19	18	4	89	2,39	1,36	5	3	2	5	3	18	56,00	8
E	Laboratory classes	13	7	24	17	22	6	89	2,52	1,48	11	4	7	5	3	30	105,00	2
	Virtual laboratory	47	20	13	3	3	3	89	0,92	1,28	1	2	1	0	1	5	17,00	24

Table 5. Survey results for Thai students [n=100]

L/O/V/E	Teaching and Learning Method	Most Applied Teaching and Learning Method							Efficient Teaching and Learning Method							Rank		
		0	1	2	3	4	5	Sum	Mean	SD	5	4	3	2	1		Sum	Sum product
	Discussion	2	21	16	23	24	14	100	2,88	1,40	5	19	10	8	5	47	152,00	3
	Demonstration with exercising	2	18	19	16	29	16	100	3,00	1,42	4	3	6	2	5	20	59,00	9
	Class debate	6	23	20	16	26	9	100	2,60	1,46	2	1	2	5	1	11	31,00	16
	Small group debate	7	23	20	14	21	15	100	2,64	1,56	2	2	9	9	8	30	71,00	7
	Simulation	6	25	21	26	13	9	100	2,42	1,38	0	5	2	8	4	19	46,00	13
	Problem-based learning	4	22	19	20	23	12	100	2,72	1,44	5	5	0	1	3	14	50,00	11
	Programmed teaching	15	26	17	19	14	9	100	2,18	1,55	1	0	0	0	1	2	6,00	25
L	Workshop	9	23	18	18	19	13	100	2,54	1,55	3	4	6	2	8	23	61,00	8
	Brainstorming	0	20	16	21	28	15	100	3,02	1,36	5	4	4	10	2	25	75,00	6
	Case study	2	19	18	14	30	17	100	3,02	1,45	13	9	10	8	11	51	158,00	2
	Online interactive learning	37	24	14	10	6	9	100	1,51	1,62	0	2	1	2	3	8	18,00	22
	Game-based learning	20	31	13	21	8	7	100	1,87	1,50	0	1	1	1	2	5	11,00	24
	Role play	21	25	15	19	11	9	100	2,01	1,59	0	0	2	0	0	2	6,00	26
	Guided practical exercises	1	15	19	25	25	15	100	3,03	1,31	10	17	3	2	5	37	136,00	4
	Assignments	1	11	10	16	29	33	100	3,60	1,37	1	4	8	12	9	34	78,00	5
	Individual presentation	1	16	24	14	32	13	100	2,99	1,35	2	0	4	5	5	16	37,00	15
	Lecture	1	7	15	5	25	47	100	3,87	1,38	31	6	4	2	8	51	203,00	1
	Guided conversation	3	15	18	17	31	16	100	3,06	1,41	0	2	5	1	3	11	28,00	18
O	Integrated or interdisciplinary teaching	3	23	17	23	24	10	100	2,72	1,39	5	2	2	5	5	19	54,00	10
	Showing video material	3	28	20	28	10	11	100	2,47	1,36	4	4	3	2	1	14	50,00	12
	Seminars conducted in class	3	25	22	17	18	15	100	2,67	1,47	1	1	4	3	2	11	29,00	17
	Live lecture from a remote place	31	29	12	10	9	9	100	1,64	1,63	0	0	1	1	0	2	5,00	27
	Field classes, trips and excursions	19	29	19	11	14	8	100	1,96	1,56	1	2	1	2	1	7	21,00	21
V	Conference	26	25	18	9	12	10	100	1,86	1,66	0	0	0	0	2	2	2,00	28
	Virtual reality	16	30	20	14	10	10	100	2,02	1,54	2	2	1	1	1	7	24,00	19
	Project-based learning	7	25	16	18	23	11	100	2,58	1,51	2	4	3	3	3	15	44,00	14
E	Laboratory classes	14	29	20	14	12	11	100	2,14	1,56	0	2	3	2	2	9	23,00	20
	Virtual laboratory	26	24	19	10	12	9	100	1,85	1,63	1	1	0	4	0	6	17,00	23